

Social and Political Activities of Women in Sindh

Author's Details:

Nasrullah Kabooro¹ Muhammad Ali Laghari² Ms. Fahmida Memon³ Ms. Farazana Sonlangi⁴ Nazia Parveen Gill⁵

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Muslim History, University of Sindh Jamshoro

² Assistant Professor, Department of Muslim History, University of Sindh Jamshoro

³ Assistant Professor, Department of Political Science, University of Sindh Jamshoro

⁴ Lecturer, Department of Muslim History, University of Sindh Jamshoro

⁵ Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics, University of Sindh, Pakistan.

Abstract:

Soon after the First World War, political reawakening got accelerated impetus in the sub-continent. The Muslim women joined hands with men in this national struggle. Thus, we find several ladies like Miss Fatima Jinnah, Begum Rana Liaquat Ali Khan, Lady Nusrat Haroon, and Begum Sughra Hidayatullah, leading the Freedom Movement and mobilizing female public opinion in favor of the demand for Pakistan. After independence, many prominent ladies worked hard in the nation- building a program to consolidate the newly born state. Some of those prominent ladies who strived to bring to Social and Political awaking among the women were Begum Rana Liaquat Ali Khan, Fatima Jinnah, Nusrat Bhutto and Muhtrama Benazir Bhutto etc. This paper reflects a brief review of the services rendered by the Sindhi women in the development of the restored province of Sindh in general and women's rights in particular. The services and the contribution of these prominent ladies have been highlighted in this article.

Keywords: Social activities, Women in Sindh

INTRODUCTION:

It is a well-known fact that Pakistan was a newly born state which came into being on 14th August 1947. Before this, the provinces, now comprising the lands of Pakistan were the part and parcel of Indian Sub-continent being ruled by the Britishers. Soon after the First World War, political reawakening intensified in the Sub- continent. By 1940, All India Muslim League to popularized the slogan of a separate homeland (Pakistan) for the Muslims in the South Asia. Muhammad Ali Jinnah was the sole leader of the Muslims of India. We are known that in Pakistan movement Muslim women also took part in achieving the goal too. Their struggle for freedom can be summarized in these words:

“The struggle to achieve Pakistan was a long and hard one. Not only men took part but women also actively participated in this glorious struggle. At that time our women observed strict purdah. They were less educated than the Hindu women. But many selfless women came forward and worked side by side with men. The struggle towards the reawakening among the Muslim women was carried by many noble ladies. The names of such women are B-Aman, Begum Muhammad Ali, Miss Fatima Jinnah, Begum Ra'ana Liaquat Ali, Lady Nusrat Haroon, Sughra Hidayat Allah, Begum Khair-un-Nissa etc. These women formed the women's branch of the Muslim League. They met wives and daughters of British officers and made them realize that their demand was just. They encouraged their brothers, husbands, and sons to continue the struggle. They addressed in public meetings and awakened the Muslims from their deep slumber. Due to their continuous efforts, Pakistan came into existence”

Although many women participated and took an active part in every walk of life but here few very important ladies are described as under. Mohtarma Fatima Jinnah the sister of Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah, worked all along with her brother worked day and night in the freedom struggle. (Zardari, Muhammad Liaq, Dr. 1984) When Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah who took over as Governor-General of the newly born state of Pakistan, her responsibilities increased. She performed her duties as the first lady of Pakistan.

Her great achievement is as an opposition leader, when she opposed, organized and struggle against military ruler Muhammad Ayooob Khan. Lastly, she contested the Presidential election of Pakistan in 1965. Ayooob Khan himself had accepted the tough times given by Miss Jinnah. While 1965 election is famous for rigging though Miss Jinnah obtained 28691 votes against President Ayooob Khan who secured 49951 votes. (Khan, Muhammad Ayub, 1947).

Miss Fatima Jinnah is followed by Begum Ra'ana Liaquat Ali Khan, Begum Sahiba was the wife of Liaquat Ali Khan a prominent leader of Pakistan Movement, who became First Prime Minister Liaquat Ali was assassinated in Rawalpindi on 16th October 1951. Begum Liaquat Ali Khan actively took part in the social life of Pakistan in general and Sindh in particular. Her great achievement is APWA, through which she brought social reawakening in the Women of Pakistan. She spread APWA, throughout the country and worked in different spheres of life. Several schools and girls, training centers were opened to enable Pakistani girls to earn jobs easily. Lastly, Begum Liaquat Ali Khan was made Governor of Sindh under the leadership of Zulfikar Ali Bhutto. She remained as Governor from 15-02-1973 to 1976. she will be remembered for long times in the social life of Sindh province.

Lady Nusrat Haroon is another name remembered even today for her services. She was the wife of Haji Abdullah Haroon. Haji Sahib was a man of vision and famous philanthropist belonging to Memon Community of Karachi. Basically, he was a businessman: he took a keen interest in the public life of Sindh province. Lastly, he became the president of Sindh Muslim League and died in this capacity of 26.5.1942. (Soomro, Muhammad Qasim, Dr. 1989) G.M.Sayed has greatly admired the role of Lady Must Haroon. Basically, she was a nurse, but her services greatly expanded after the marriage with Haji Abdullah Haroon. Haji Sahib took an active part in the Freedom Movement of Muslim League not only to assist his wife but to bring a political consciousness in the masses. Begum Sahiba herself got political training from the mother of eminent Ali brothers. She was appointed as Chairperson of All India Muslim League held in Lahore, Allahabad, Madras and Karachi. She remained Vice – President of All Pakistan Women Association. There are so many other social services to her credit. (Syed, G.M. 1947) . Soon before and after partition, we have names of Begum Mariam Hatim Badurdin Tayabji and Mrs. Gul Bano K. Men wall- famous for the social services in Karachi.

Begum Tahira, Agha Ijaz Hussain, is famous for her political and social career. She was born and educated in Hyderabad, won the seat in Sindh Assembly in 1953. Then she became a member of the West Pakistan Assembly during One Unit (1955-1970). Earlier she worked hard for Sindh Muslim League and is remembered as an active worker of Pakistan movement. She wrote two booklets for this purpose namely ” Our Pakistan “ and ” Quaid –e- Azam “ the both were in Sindh? Apart from this Begum Tahira took an active part in the social, educational and cultural life of Sindh and Pakistan. She also remained a member of Syndicate of Sindh University (Syed, G.M. 1979).

Begum Nusrat Bhutto is a prominent name in Pakistani women. She was a widow of Late Zulfikar Ali Bhutto, who had been the President and the Prime Minister of Pakistan. Begum Sahiba is a learned lady. During the seventies, women branch of Pakistan people's party was established and she became its first Chairperson. She was elected as a member of National Assembly of Pakistan and worked hard for the development of country along with her husband during his rule. Bhutto Sahib was removed by General Ziaul Haq (July 1977) and kept behind the bars. Begum Nusrat Bhutto became on acting Chairperson of Pakistan people's Party. Her Political career and struggle were inevitable, which she played during Zia regime. she became senior Federal Minister during Benazir Government (1988-1990) as well.

One unit was dissolved on 01.07.1970 and four historic provinces Sindh, Punjab, K.P.K and Baluchistan were created in the West Pakistan. From 1970 we can see clearly in different walks of life, the women of Sindh are working shoulder to shoulder with agents for the uplift of society. There are several fields in which Sindhi women are ahead. It may be social sector or education. It may be a cultural aspect or political. We find women active in all these portions of society. Here we will concentrate only on some important examples. Miss Benazir (Born in 1953) was the daughter of Late Zulfikar Ali Bhutto, she was educated in Europe and America and married with Asif Ali Zardari (on December 18th, 1987), she was the author of many books, a good orator, a daughter of Sindh province. Her role against Zia regime and for the restoration of democracy in Pakistan is indeed a memorable character and may long be remembered in the annals of her father's death. (Benzair Bhutto 1989). Benazir became the Prime Minister of Pakistan twice

(1988-1990). She returned to Pakistan in 2007 but was assassinated by terrorists in Rawalpindi on 27th December 2007.

We have a long list of Sindhi political women, who took an active part in the politics women of Sindh or Pakistan. Akhtar Baloch appeared on the scene in the early seventies. She was an emotional worker and dedicated her life for the rights of Sindh during Yahaya Khan regime (1969-1971) (Kachelive, Mahar 1985) Begum Zakia Brohi: got her education in Karachi and Larkana, married with M. Iqbal Brohi of Larkana in 1957. She has been an active worker of Pakistan Peoples Party and lastly became Chairperson of Hyderabad divisional branch of the party. She became a member of Sindh Assembly for health and education sectors. (Kachelive, Mahar 1985) Noor - Jehan Soomro remained an active worker of Pakistan People's party in Karachi, and due to her enthusiasm for the party, she was elected as a member of Sindh Assembly during Bhutto period. During Zia regime, for some time she was imprisoned. (Kachelive, Mahar 1985)

Taj Babi Baloch also belonged to PPP and was elected Sindh Assembly member in 1972. She also went to Jail for the party. She belongs to Karachi division. (Kachelive, Mahar 1985)

Begum Shamim N.D. Khan belongs to Urdu speaking community of Karachi. She remained in PPP along with her husband Professor N.D. Khan. She worked as General Secretary of Ladies Wing for Sindh province of PPP. Begum Shamim proved herself as an emotional worker during Zia regime. She played an active role during anti-Zia movement and was sent to prison for several times along with her husband. She proved herself loyal with Begum Nusrat and Benazir Bhutto, after the demise of Bhutto (1979). (Kachelive, Mahar 1985)

After the Zia government when Benazir became Prime Minister of Pakistan, Shamim N.D. Khan remained in public life in several posts. Indeed it was PPP and its leader Mr. Zulfikar Ali Bhutto, who encouraged women from every corner of Sindh and Pakistan, who played an active role in public life. There are few other names in this regard. Firdous Junejo, Begum Bashir Abro, Begum Ashraf Abbasi, Fatima Soomro, Ruqia Soomro, Seema Rafique, Shimmel Chandio, Begum Gulzar, Razia Mahar and Shahida Nafees Siddiqui- are famous political workers belonged to PPP. (Kachelive, Mahar 1985)

Ziaul Haque regime (1977)-1988) introduced some new characters among Pakistani women. In Sindh, several ladies appeared on the social, political, educational and medical sectors of Pakistan society. I shall mention few important names here. These are Dr. Ameena Ashraf, Khanum Gohar, Begum Afridi, Begum Gulzar under, Begum Salma Ahmed, Mrs. Rashid Pasha Khuhro, Mrs. Parveen Mari and Begum Mumtaz Noorani. (Kachelive, Mahar 1985) Sindh has produced a good number of women educationists, during fifty years of Pakistan history. Mrs. Shams Abbasi belongs to Hyderabad's famous Qazi family. Basically, a teacher Shams Abbasi has worked on different administrative posts in Sindh education department. In the last days of service, she even did Ph.D. from Sindh University. Recently her autobiography has also been published.

Dr. Hamida Khuhro belongs to Larkana and was the daughter of famous leader Muhammad Ayoob Khuhro. She had Ph. D in History from London University. Earlier she was a lecturer, then joined Karachi University and lastly Sindh University Jamshoro as Professor of History. Dr. Khuhro remained education minister of Sindh during Dr. Arbab Ghulam Rahim ministry Apart from her political career, her name was famous as a historian. She was considered to be an authority on the modern history of Sindh. Her famous books are as " the making of Sindh " " Documents of separation of Sindh from the Bombay Presidency " Vol.1. & II (1982) and " Karachi: Megacity of our time" (1997). She died on 13th February 2017.

Mrs. Mehtab Akbar Rashidi belongs to Naudero, district Larkana Sindh. Started a career as a school teacher and then joined the University of Sindh as a teacher of International Relations, where she became a Professor, Meantime she was appointed as a Director, Institute of Sindhology, where she earned fame. She also did M.Sc. in International Relation from the University of Massachusetts (USA). Her dissertation " Indo – Pak Relations " was published by Pakistan Sind Centre, the University of Sindh in 1988. Mehtab Rashdi is also famous as Radio – announcer and T.V. compare, she has known personality across Pakistan. (Athar, Khalid 1987). She served as secretary to various Sindh government departments. Currently, she is MPA Sindh Assembly and belongs to PML (F) party. After the establishment of Pakistan, women of

Sindh have served, with love and labor even in Sindhi Languages and Literature. Several volumes of novels, short stories, essays, poems are being produced by Sindhi ladies. There are scores of women who are dedicated to language and literature. Mehtab Mehboob, Mariam Kajidi, Durr Shawar Sayed. Noorul – Huda Shah, Rashida Hijab, Zarina Baloch, Akhtar Baloch and others have a number of books to their credit. (Sindhi, Memon Abdul Majeed, 1993). Begum Mumtaz Rashdi and Mrs. Farzana Panhwar, though not – Sindhi's by birth but married in Sindhi families, are prominent women of Sindh. Mrs. Mumtaz Rashdi has a learned lady and had few books to her credit. But she is indeed known as an agriculturist lady. Mrs. Farzana Panhwar is now known worldwide as an agriculture scientist and has on to her credit several papers on agriculture.

CONCLUSION:

The development and achievement of Sindh women during past fifty years is indeed a miracle and it has become possible only after the creation of Pakistan. Though this process is slow but not disappointing. While Islamic reawakening in Afghanistan and Iran are going to limit the activities of women but our new government is working on progressive lines. The proof of this lies in the fact that Syeda Shela Raza, women, has been elected as Deputy Speaker of Sindh Assembly and score of women have also been elected as MPA's and MNA's on Special women Quetta and general Quite So we are hopeful about the bright future of women in Sindh.

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